

Research ethics & bioethics at Uppsala University 2023

Annual report from the Centre for Research Ethics
& Bioethics (CRB) at Uppsala University

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About the Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB)

The Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB) explores current ethical issues through philosophical, empirical and normative approaches. Our work builds capacity and contributes to the knowledge base for research & innovation, policy, management and clinical practice.

CRB is an interfaculty centre that is governed by a board of University representatives and led by a Director. The Centre is administratively associated with the Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences at the Faculty of Medicine, where all Centre staff are employed. At the Department level, Niklas Juth, Professor in Clinical Medical Ethics serves as a research group leader and answers to the Department board. The Centre is led by Director Stefan Eriksson, Associate Professor and Senior Lecturer in Research Ethics, who answers to the Centre board. Both roles are supported by Coordinator Josepine Fernow.

This report was written by Josepine Fernow, with contributions from Anna Holm Bodin, Niklas Juth, Stefan Eriksson & Malin Rick Folkegård.

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Contents of this report

Research at the Centre	2
Our approach to teaching ethics.....	2
Societal engagement.....	3
The Centre in numbers.....	3
Internal funding mechanisms.....	5
Centre activities for disciplinary domains	6
Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics.....	7
External research funding.....	8
Communication & dissemination	9
Developing a new profile.....	9
Our outreach in numbers	10
Want to know more?	10

Research at the Centre

We identify and explore current ethical issues through conceptual, normative, and empirical approaches. Our research is both fundamental and applied: providing conceptual tools and hands-on guidance for stakeholders in research, policy, clinical practice, and beyond, in six areas:

Healthcare, public health & professional ethics: Focusing on ethical issues raised in clinical practice and care, preventive programmes, and healthcare management. Examining policy, organisation, professional roles and value conflicts.

Biomedicine, biobanks & genomics: Focusing on the ethical and societal aspects of genetic genomic data collection, storage and use in biobank and registry studies, and the translation of biomedical research results into clinical applications.

Research ethics & academic integrity: Focusing on value conflicts and ethical issues related to research practice: providing a bridge from research ethics to academic integrity by guiding informed consent, academic publishing, and good research practice.

Brain, consciousness & artificial intelligence: Focusing on ethical, social and philosophical questions raised by artificial intelligence, neuroscience and brain research, consciousness and cognition, and the idea and use of digital twins.

Food, medicine & environment: Focusing on the value conflicts and ethical dilemmas that we experience as individuals, patients and professionals in relation to what we eat, the medicines we use, and where we live.

Policy, engagement & communication: Focusing on current ethical issues together with stakeholders. Our work provides insights on how to communicate with citizens, patients and professionals about research, risk and individual responsibility.

Our approach to teaching ethics

Students, scientists, professionals and decision-makers all experience ethical dilemmas. The Centre provides ethics teaching and training for undergraduate, master and PhD students at Uppsala University, and offers flexible training modules for staff. We provide tools to explore the values at stake and reflect on and manage ethical problems. We believe that good education rests on a solid foundation of research. Good teaching begins with the teacher's own knowledge and competence. Questions are at the core of training and education, with examination becoming an integrated part of learning. We aim to help students and colleagues develop their competence, allowing them to identify the values at stake when they are faced with ethical dilemmas in their professional life or research. Ethics teaching is not about teaching students what to think.

Exercises in critical thinking provide students with an opportunity to practice critical analysis and allow them to evaluate arguments for and against different opinions. For this reason, most of our teaching is interactive. We combine theoretical knowledge with practice and often start the discussion with actual cases and research ethics or medical ethics dilemmas. Our teaching combines theoretical knowledge with discussions of current real-life cases and questions that connect to student's everyday experiences.

Societal engagement

We take the third task of the University seriously and actively engage with stakeholders to build ethical competence, promote good research practice, and support the uptake of research results through tailored & targeted science communication.

Our research develops knowledge about **ethical competence** and contributes to understanding the values at stake. Our collaboration with the Region of Uppsala provides clinical ethics support for decision-makers and practitioners.

The Centre is instrumental in driving Uppsala University's work to develop **good research practice, research ethics & academic integrity**. Our efforts include generating knowledge about the laws, regulations and ethical guidelines that govern research, operationalised in our research efforts, education, link libraries, provision of expertise, guidance and information.

For many years, the Centre has made a coordinated effort to develop tools and channels for **science communication**. We use blogs and other channels to reflect on the impact of research and people's understanding of science. We also support uptake of research results with tailored science communication tools and tactics for different stakeholder groups, and lead efforts to communicate, disseminate and develop impact strategy in several European projects.

The Centre in numbers

In 2023, total funding for Centre activities amounted to 23 488 624 SEK. In addition to Centre funding provided by the disciplinary domains (2 661 000 SEK), funding for activities is generated and received from multiple sources. In total, faculty funding for the research group amounts to 6 525 969 SEK, of which 2 391 202 SEK (36%) is funding related to the Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics; external research grants amount to 12 973 474 SEK; with 1 327 181 generated through teaching.

Centre & group total revenue: 23 488 624 SEK

With 27 employees and 9 associated researchers in 2023, CRB is by far the largest bioethics and research ethics research environment in Sweden. In 2023, the group of PhD students grew from three to five.

Full-time equivalents 2023

Translated to employee full-time equivalents, the Centre workforce comprises researchers and postdocs, with senior lecturers representing only 3% of the total staff effort in 2023. To fill existing gaps, two half-time senior lecturers were recruited, and both positions were filled in early 2024. In addition, the Centre's teaching effort is supported by all staff members, including doctoral students and technical/administrative staff. One additional science communicator was hired in 2023 to support the development of four new websites for the Centre and projects.

In addition to employees, the Centre's dynamic and multi-disciplinary research environment includes a substantial group of associated researchers and one PhD student employed by the Region of Sörmland. During the year, the Centre also hosted two visiting scholars: Anna Hirsch, postdoc philosopher and bioethicist from Ludwig-Maximilians Universität München (one month, focusing on children's right to autonomy in healthcare), and Borgar Jølstad, psychologist and doctoral student in medical ethics from Akershus Universitetssykehus Oslo (3 months, focus on severity as a priority setting criterion in healthcare).

Internal funding mechanisms

A large part of the Centre's funding is performance-based, generating 2 551 936 SEK for publications (658 607), examination of students (662 089), and external research funding (1 231 240). In 2023, 15 groups at the Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences received performance-based faculty funding, with the Centre being the largest recipient: generating 22,4 % of the total performance-based funding for the Department.

Another large portion of the Centre's budget is based on teaching. The Centre offers three master-level courses for 7,5 credits each at the Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences, covering neuroethics, ethics and public health & ethics in research, writing and communication. We are responsible for the ethics training in several programmes at Uppsala University, including the Medical doctor's programme; Nursing programme; Specialist nursing programme; Midwives programme; Engineering programme in molecular biotechnology; Teacher education in natural sciences and biology; Master's programme in public health; Master's programme in infection biology; Master's Programmes in forensic science, molecular medicine, precision medicine and innovative medicine.

In addition to teaching undergraduate and master-level students, we provide teaching for PhD students in medicine & pharmacy on research ethics (with 147 students in 2023) and popular science writing (132 students in 2023), and research ethics for science & technology (70 students in 2023). As part of our efforts for the disciplinary domains at Uppsala University, we also provide flexible training modules that have been used in courses for doctoral students in other disciplinary domains.

In addition, the Centre received a faculty contribution towards rent (746 883 SEK) and a 300 000 contribution from the Centre for Medical Humanities graduate school for a PhD project on ethical dilemmas and ethical competence related to providing dietary advice in primary care.

Centre activities for disciplinary domains

The Centre received 2,661,000 SEK from the three disciplinary domains as a foundation for the mission to provide research ethics teaching, initiate research and provide expertise. Together with the research group and Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics, the centre provides critical mass and creates synergies, for example through the dual role of Centre Director Stefan Eriksson, who also serves as an advisor to the Vice Chancellor on Good Research Practice; and leader of a group of confidants appointed by the disciplinary domains to provide support and advice, platforms for knowledge sharing and capacity building, training, and advice on ethics review.

Centre funding: 2 661 000 SEK

The Centre provides expertise and hands-on guidance for staff through modular training, and online resources for staff, providing information, tools, resources, and guidelines for different needs and aspects of ethics in research and academic practice. During 2023, the Centre also provided this information for external audiences through the Codex website (www.codex.uu.se), first developed in 2000 with support from the Swedish Research Council. However, as many actors are now providing online resources, from May 2024, this resource will no longer be openly available. Instead, the Codex resource will be integrated into the Uppsala University research handbook.

Another long-term public online resource: The Ethics Blog and its Swedish-language counterpart Etikbloggen, have been publishing reflective content about research and research practice since 2011. The blog is published weekly and reaches around 7,000 email subscribers. With 887 posts since the start, a total of 62 posts were published in 2023 (31 on each blog).

The Centre's flexible training modules are currently being used in our own courses and training, and other courses at Uppsala University (e.g. Forskningsetik och kommunikation at the Department of Modern Languages). They are also used in the national Research Ethics for Researchers in Medicine course (mandatory for future supervisors) developed jointly by all Universities that offer the medical doctor's programme.

The Centre organises a series of open higher seminars conducted jointly with the Stockholm Centre for Healthcare Ethics (CHE), a collaborative centre established by Karolinska Institutet, the Royal Institute of Technology, and Stockholm University. In 2023, the series included 22 seminars for staff and occasional invited guests to discuss and enhance unpublished work, primarily benefiting junior

researchers by promoting academic discourse and skill development in a supportive setting. PhD students at the Centre earn academic credits for participating.

We share our expertise as invited speakers at the University and across the world. In 2023, the Centre's expertise was often called for to discuss (for example) the use of AI in research and education, ethics review, scientific misconduct, predatory publishing, priorities, information and cognitive impairment, citizen science, children participating in research, research in emergency care settings, withdrawal of life-support, and perceptions of consciousness in psychiatric care.

In 2023, the Centre took over responsibility for organising the largest annual Swedish conference on medical ethics. The Call for Abstracts was published in December. The UMEC conference will be held from 10-11 June 2024. It is the third in a series, first organised by Lund University in 2022, followed by Karolinska Institutet (KIMEC) in 2023.

Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics

The Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics includes research as well as teaching for the Medical doctor's programme on the ethics of euthanasia, paediatric care, obstetric & gynaecological care, and priority setting in health care but also the teaching of doctoral students and healthcare professionals at Region Uppsala. 20% of the Chair's salary is covered by a grant from Vetenskapsrådet (Just Severity). The 3-year temporary funding (etableringsbidrag) has been used to establish a platform for research on clinical medical ethics at the Centre through two projects: One PhD project that started in November 2022, where Adam Ehlerth builds on this work by looking at severity as a priority setting criterion in healthcare. In 2023, the project strengthened existing collaborations with the National Centre for Priority Setting in Health Care at Linköping University (through the Just Severity project); and the Institute of Clinical Medicine at the University of Oslo (through the Norwegian sister-project SEVPRI). The second project is focused on interventions with no or questionable consent, so-called "soft coercion", in research and somatic healthcare, employing two part-time researchers (Joar Björk & Tove Godskesen), an initiative that has reinforced research collaborations in Sweden (with researchers at Karolinska Institutet looking into compulsory care) and abroad (Anna Hirsch, Ludwig-Maximilians Universität München) that has strengthened CRB's profile as leading in clinical medical ethics.

Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics: 2 391 202 SEK

50% of the Professor's chair in clinical medical ethics is funded by the Region of Uppsala, where the Professor chairs the regional Ethics Council, and provides advice in ethically difficult cases. The Ethics Council works to strengthen ethical competence in health care. The Council meets every two months to discuss ethical issues raised by either the Region's healthcare sector or the Council themselves, often covering more principal issues. In 2023, the Council addressed the government's suggestion to make it mandatory for healthcare personnel to report illegal immigrants to authorities, the increased use of AI in healthcare, the Region's suggestion to allow women the choice of having a hospital or supervised home birth, historical cases where sperm donated for research was used in fertility treatments without consent, and more. Through these discussions, the Council provides direct policy feedback for the Region. In addition, the Council is responsible for organising ethics seminars for healthcare personnel (e.g. on priority setting), providing training and education in ethical analysis (e.g. for obstetrics, gynaecology, and paediatrics), and supporting local councils' ethics work within the Region.

In addition to the Region of Uppsala, the Centre is collaborating with the Region of Sörmland, which is currently funding one PhD project on the transformation of family medicine (Allmänmedicin under omvandling: Hur påverkar en ökad detaljstyrning allmänmedicinens praktik?) and a research project on general practitioners' experiences of stress (GPStress: Mellanmänskliga och kontextuella orsaker till stress i allmänmedicinska konsultationer - en fokusgruppsstudie). Moreover, the Region's Ethics Council has established cooperation with corresponding councils and networks in other regions, foremost in Dalarna, Gävleborg, Stockholm (Karolinska universitetssjukhuset), and Göteborg (Sahlgrenska sjukhuset).

External research funding

Most of our research is funded through different European collaborative funding schemes. During 2024, we were involved in BRIDGE: Bridging Integrity in Higher Education, Business and Society (Erasmus + Strategic Partnership), CAVAA: Counterfactual Assessment and Valuation for Awareness Architecture (European Innovation Council); ConcePTION: Building an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating of medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding – validated and regulatory endorsed workflows for fast, optimised evidence generation (Innovative Medicines Initiative); ENLIGHTENme: Innovative policies for improving citizens' health and wellbeing addressing indoor and outdoor lighting (Horizon 2020); Human Brain Project (EU FET Flagship); MINDtheGEPs: Modifying Institutions by Developing Gender Equality Plans (Horizon 2020);

Neurotwin: Digital twins for model-driven non-invasive electrical brain stimulation (Horizon 2020); Screen4Care: Shortening the path to rare disease diagnosis by using newborn genetic screening and digital technologies (Innovative Medicines Initiative).

The Swedish Research Council is the second largest funding agency. In addition to the European collaborations funded through the ERA PerMed programme (RELIABLE: Targeting subclinical motor and cognitive impairment in patients with early onset Multiple Sclerosis at high Risk of disEase acitivity through a preventive personaLised and InnovAtive rehaBiLitation strategy; ONCOLOGICS: AI-based decision support for better treatment of colorectal cancer; & MEET-AML: Metabolic vulnerabilities for personalized therapeutic approaches in acute myeloid leukemia), we are also involved in the following projects funded directly by the Swedish Research Council: In the best interest of the child? Ethical, legal and empirical assessments of decisions in social service to restrict social contact; Just Severity: Severity as a priority setting criterion in healthcare; & Strain a gnat & swallow a camel? Ethical review of humanities and social sciences fit for purpose.

Projects funded by other agencies include AICare: AI and Automated systems and the Right to Health - Revisiting law accounting for the exploitation of users' preferences and values (WASP-HS); Providing dietary advice in primary care (Uppsala University, Centre for Medical Humanities); Public perceptions of cancer risk (Swedish Cancer Society); and RUBIKS: Ethical and clinical aspects of recruiting children with cancer to research (Swedish Childhood Cancer Society).

Communication & dissemination

We actively engage in debate and collaborate with stakeholders through both research activities and media. The Centre has a strong science communications profile, disseminating results through our website, X/Twitter, two research blogs (Etikbloggen and The Ethics Blog), a Centre Zenodo community, and YouTube. The Centre's expertise on the impact and uptake of results plays an important role in research at the Centre. We also lead communication and dissemination efforts in several EU projects. During 2023, these projects included MINDtheGEPs (Horizon 2020), ConcePTION (Innovative Medicines Initiative), and the Human Brain Project's RRI work package (EU FET Flagship).

In addition to the Centre's website, we host websites for several ongoing and completed projects (H2020 SIENNA, H2020 MINDtheGEPs & IMI PREFER). Thus, the decision to migrate all websites hosted by Uppsala University to a new IT platform had a significant impact on the workload in 2023. This also affected the CODEX website, which will transform from a publicly available web page to an Uppsala University internal resource.

Developing a new profile

The effort to develop a new website provided an opportunity to develop an updated profile for the Centre. A SWOT workshop was organised in June, identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for communication, to guide how the Centre and research group are presented in external channels. The workshop resulted in a decision to highlight our joint focus on ethical, philosophical and societal issues; and focus on how this is operationalised in research, teaching, training, and societal engagement; and how we create value with and for stakeholders, by both identifying and addressing ethical, societal and conceptual concerns. Audiences for external communications are prioritised in the following order: peers; potential collaborators; professionals looking for training; research, education and funding organisations; policy makers, civil society organisations, press, and publics; and

lastly students). A November workshop discussing Centre activities informed the development of key messages, which were then incorporated into our new Centre website, launched on April 5, 2024 (www.uu.se/crb or www.uu.se/centre/crb).

Our outreach in numbers

In 2023, researchers at the Centre published 55 peer-reviewed publications, with 42% reaching an Altmetric score over 10 (top 25%). The highest score, 682, was reached by a publication about AI detection tools¹. We were featured in public media discussions on ethics in higher education and research, maternal medicine safety, healthcare priorities, and neuroethics, appearing in over 10 media outlets. Sometimes interviewed as experts, sometimes as authors of opinion texts.

The Centre's official website, www.crb.uu.se (www.uu.se/centre/crb from April 5, 2024), is an information hub for projects, publications, and personnel. It includes dynamic content such as the Ethics Blog feed and news from the Centre. Our blog posts and news items are shared on the CRB's Twitter/X (@crb_uu), with 749 followers (end of March 2024). During 2023, our X account attracted 132 new followers, and we posted 112 tweets from April to December 2023, in turn attracting over 6,600 profile visits. The average engagement rate for the Centre's content is high, 5.6%, compared to the average 1.5% overall engagement rate on the X/Twitter platform.

Want to know more?

Web: www.uu.se/crb

Blog: www.ethicsblog.crb.uu.se / www.etikbloggen.crb.uu.se

Follow us on X: https://twitter.com/crb_uu

Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/crb/>

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@crb_uu

¹ Weber-Wulff, D., Anohina-Naumeca, A., Bjelobaba, S. *et al.* Testing of detection tools for AI-generated text. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 19, 26 (2023). DOI: 10.1007/s40979-023-00146-z